

Vitamin Deficiency and Food Recommendation System Using Machine Learning

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Abstract:

According to a WHO study, inadequate and inadequate food consumption is to blame for 14% of colon cancer deaths, 11% of deaths from ischemic heart disease, and 9% of deaths from heart conditions worldwide. Additionally, between 0.25 billion and 0.7 billion people worldwide experience iodine deficiency, 0.2 billion adults experience iron deficiency , and 0.25 billion children experience various vitamin deficiencies ranging from A to K. This project's main objective is to recommend a diet to various people. The dataset's enormous volume of data must be handled by the proposed framework.

I. INTRODUCTION

Humans today deal with a wide range of health problems, such as problems with fitness, poor food, mental health problems, and so forth. Additionally, 0.7 billion individuals lack iodine, 0.2 billion people have an iron deficiency, and 0.25 billion youngsters are vitamin A deficient. The amount of data the recommendation engine must manage is substantial. separating out the information that is much more valuable using an operating system and other criteria that take the user's preferences and interests into account. The three steps of recommender systems are

the information gathering step, the learning phase, and the recommendations phase. Prior to classifying the many solutions to a given problem, information must first be acquired describing that problem. After data is collected, the learning phase, during which different inferences are formed from the data, and the recommendation phase are both initiated. There is an output that includes a number of suggestions. Our project's suggestion output is based on the customer's physical traits, preferences. In most cases, a person is unaware of the major causes of deficiency or illness.

The goal of this project is to create a system that will advise users on proper nutrition intake based on their BMI and grocery data preferences. Most of the time, a person is ignorant of the main factors contributing to a deficiency or illness. Most of the time, a person is ignorant of the main factors contributing to a deficiency. Under weight, overweight, and obese are all weight status categories calculated by BMI.

II. LITERATURE SURVEY

The meal plan for the individual recommended using their preferences. Both user choices and nutritional information are recorded by this application. Data mining technology, according to Vijay Jaiswal, might be used to monitor things like calorie burn, eating patterns, and healthy eating habits. With this technique, hidden patterns and customer eating habits are found utilising a variety of data sources. The decision tree learning algorithm used in this tool makes use of random tree techniques on a variety of datasets. H. Jiang offered a strategy for figuring out daily caloric needs. Utilizing the Knapsack algorithm, suggested user diet combinations are generated. In contrast to previous diabetes diet recommendations systems, this one might score the foods.

III. EXISTING SYSTEM

It is suggested to develop a content-based food recommender system that tailors food dishes to a user's preferences. The ingredients in the user's most popular recipes are split down, and each is given a rating based on the preferences of previous users. The suggested recipes make use of the same item. Furthermore, since the user's tastes could not change every day, identical recommendations are feasible.

Latent factors and tags are employed for an android-based meal recommendation system. The system presents the user with a personalised recipe that is based on the tags and ratings they have provided in their preferences. The proposed system's approach made use of matrix factorization and latent feature vectors. Prediction accuracy is increased by the use of tags that closely match recommendations with consumer preferences.

IV. PROPOSED SYSTEM

The accuracy of vitamin deficiency and diet recommendations are checked using a variety of machine learning methods, and the best model is chosen for prediction in the Flask web application. The computer detects vitamin deficiency and offers meal suggestions when the user enters vitamin values. Their are five modules in this and every module has its own functions:

1. Data collection
2. Data preprocessing
3. Testing training
4. Initializing Multiple Algorithms
5. Predict data

V. ADVANTAGES

- Accuracy of model is improved when compared to existing methods.
- Efficiency of the model is improved.
- For training and testing previous datasets are used.
- It automatically process the vitamin deficiency and recommends food.

VI. ARCHITECTURE

VII . RESULT

VIII . CONCLUSION

We created a website that forecasts vitamin shortage and offers meal recommendations. Utilizing data on vitamins and vitamin deficiencies,

we implemented prediction. The first step in training the algorithm is the compilation of a dataset of food products dependent on the vitamin shortfall.

The forecasting of different dietary suggestions depending on the vitamins needed for each type of insufficiency. After clustering, the Random Forest classifier suggests the nearby foods that are most suited for the recommended diet. Based on vitamin deficiency, our diet counsel approach merely enables consumers to acquire the nutritious meals they desire.

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